

Geothermal for Peace: Exploration and development of the large Bidu-Dubbi geothermal prospect along the border of Ethiopia (Bidu Woreda, Afar Regional State) and Eritrea (Southern Denkhalya subregion, Southern Red Sea Region).

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ABSTRACT

Bidu was for a long time known as the “Bidu Sultanate”, whose resistant Sultan Yassin Haysma was captured and killed by Mussolini’s army in 1931 at the age of 39. This traditional Afar region was divided between Ethiopia to the West and Eritrea to the East. It now forms the Bidu Woreda of the Afar Regional State in Ethiopia, and the Southern Denkhalya subregion of the southern Red Sea Region in Eritrea. This region is characterized geologically by an important volcanic system trending NE-SW, in a transverse direction with respect to the dominant “Red Sea” trend (NNW-SSE). The area is characterized by the presence of 3 large recent-quadernary strato-volcanoes with calderas with diameters ranging from 5 to 8 Km, with an extension NE in the large Dubbi lava field, and one smaller silicic cone SE. Nabro, the largest, is known for its recent volcanic eruptions (2011-2012). It is located in Eritrea as Dubbi, also historically active. Mallahle, and Sork’Ale volcano are located in Ethiopia and are characterized by fumarolic activity another older caldera is partly buried under more recent volcanic products SW of Mallahle. Dubbi is dominantly made of fissure basaltic eruptions of which the last reached the Red Sea in 1861. All are characterized by complex volcanic evolution, with polycyclic silicic pyroclastic eruptions and various post-caldera events, both basaltic and rhyolitic, within and around the caldera walls. Thermal activity (fumaroles, hot and wet grounds, steam vents) are observed along faults in this transverse direction as well as parallel to the Red Sea, and along the ring faults of the two main calderas.

This volcanic alignment is closing to the south the Arrata bock (earlier called “Danakil Alps”) which is known as a lithospheric microplate rotating between the Southern Red Sea Rift and the Afar Rift. The geology of the area is composed of Pre-Cambrian basement covered by the Mesozoic sedimentary sequence. The area was deeply faulted and intruded by peralkaline granite in the Miocene during the early stage of extension of the Afro-Arabic plate boundary. The Bidu volcanic alignment is in fact part of a major transverse discontinuity that trends in a NE –SW direction. In the Red Sea, it is well visible in the Hanish islands, where the volcanic axis of the main island is built along the same NE-SW fault line. This volcano-tectonic structure marks the end of the Red Sea trough which is the active spreading axis of this young oceanic ridge. Within Afar, this marks the southern end of Tat’Ali and Alayta spreading segments and the transfer of the spreading axis to the Manda Harraro Range. Further west the Dabbayra

volcanic range is built along the same NE-SW direction, which also marks a major discontinuity in the Nubian escarpment. Several other geothermal sites are found along the same major transform fault line and fracture zone.

We have all the components for geothermal potential sites on the Ethiopia and Eritrea border. A perspective of major interest for the current Ethio-Eritrean initiative for Peace which should benefit from the support of concerned Multilateral, African regional and bilateral Agencies. Starting the exploration and development of this area of major geothermal interest should be considered as a priority target, given its unique social, environmental and economic perspective. This should be engaged in partnership with the local Afar communities, which already use the thermal vents for the production of water by condensation of the steam. The project should therefore target a cascade development including electricity production, direct uses of the thermal energy and water production. The geothermal sites would also provide for the electricity needs of the surrounding towns, including the port of Assab once it is reopened to the traffic with Ethiopia.

1. Introduction

The Afar triangle is known as one of the most active part of the Earth as three major rift systems cross each other there: The Red Sea to the north, the Gulf of Aden to the East and the East African Rift System (EARS) to the south (Tazieff et al., 1972; Beyene & Abdelsalam 2005; Bosworth et al., 2005; Varet, 2018a). Surrounded by high plateaus corresponding to the edge of the three plate margins which tend to separate since Miocene dividing the earlier Afro-Arabian plate - itself resulting from the Pre-Cambrian Pan-African Orogeny - it is also considered as resulting from the influence of a hot mantle plume forming a single dome that predated the rift systems. This dry low-land, largely below sea level (Figure 1), is populated by the dominantly pastoralist Afar people which share a common language and way of life. As a result of recent history, the Afar triangle is at present part of Eritrea to the North-East, Djibouti to the South-East and Ethiopia for its main – central-southern – part (Figure 2).

Figure 1: Relief map of the Afar triangle, with the toponymy of the main units cited in the text. The Bidu-Dubbi volcanic alignment trending NE-SW is seen as a high relief south of Arrata block.

- . NNW-SSE NW-SE trending Axial Ranges (dominantly basaltic spreading segments) are named in blue.
- . Central silicic volcanoes (including Bidu) in red.
- . Lakes in white.
- . Miocene peralkaline granitic massifs in red over yellow.
- . Transverse ranges of the margins in thick black.

Figure. 2 : The Afar triangle, a depressed area surrounded by the Nubian, Yemen and Somalian plateaus, in the area of junction of the Gulf of Aden, the Red Sea and the Main East African Rift Valley, as seen - enlightened in yellow - on this relief map, also showing the political boundaries (in red) of concerned countries: Ethiopia, Eritrea, Djibouti, Somalia and Yemen. Apart from the rather arid Afar endoreic basins, observe the mainly diverging flow pattern of the rivers. A red quadrangle marks the area of interest for a geothermal initiative for peace along the Ethio-Eritrean border.

Whereas the central-southern Afar benefits from the permanent flow of the Awash river, northern Afar is rather dry, particularly on its eastern side, when the western part benefits from some short river sheds along the border of the Nubian plateau. However, along the Red Sea side, a mountainous area called “Danakil Alps” by the first geologists (see references of the first geological explorations compiled by Dainelli, 1943), benefits from less dry conditions, with summits topping 2200m in Bidu area. This is the place where large stratovolcanoes developed with calderas, subject of the present paper, as these are also geothermal sites of interest. The whole area was mapped (Figure 3) and studied by the CNR-CNRS Afar team in the years 1967-1976 (Barberi et al. 1970; Varet, 2019);

Considering the favorable geodynamic conditions, geothermal energy was seen as a potential source of energy, both for Ethiopia and Eritrea. However, since the first reconnaissance works engaged with UNDP (1973) no real development occurred in the region, despite some exploration works engaged in both countries.

In Eritrea, both Alid and Nabro were identified as potential targets (Yohannes, 2015) but only Alid was really investigated (Duffield et al., 1997), although not yet recognized by deep drilling. This results from the fact that, until now, it has been quite difficult to envisage any kind of geothermal development in this area due to the unrest resulting from the conflict between Eritrea and Ethiopia. But since a few months, both countries entered in a process of reconciliation which allows to consider peaceful relations including socioeconomic perspectives of common interest.

As a consequence, in the present case - as along several other borders between countries which are parts of the EARS (Varet, 2018 b & c) - geothermal resources should benefit from specific attention in order to be properly studied and developed. It happens that, in several cases, geothermal resource being linked with volcanic units at higher altitude, borders would cross through these areas. As a consequence, some sites of major interest may hence appear to be removed from the respective countries’ development axis. It is particularly the case for the area subject of the present study, which do not even benefit yet from easy access conditions. This paper aims at underlining the priority that multilateral and bilateral financing agencies should consider for the present project, as it concerns a geothermal site of high potential that would

bring a perspective of peace and socio-economic development, fighting poverty in an area particularly affected by draughts resulting from climate change.

Figure 3: Location of the Bidu-Dubbi geothermal target (green quadrangle) on a Geological sketch map of Afar (modified from Varet, 1975; Beyene & Abdelsalam, 2005) showing the location of the volcanic units of Afar (from Miocene to present). Miocene units (earlier continental rift type) are located along both sides of the now stabilized margins of eastern and western Afar. Most of the Afar floor is covered by the dominantly basaltic stratoid series. During the last million year, the activity concentrated in Axial ranges (in red), as well as in marginal centres (in violet) and transverse units (in orange).

2. Geology of Bidu-Dubbi area

2.1 The geological succession

2.1.1 Precambrian basement and its Mesozoic cover

The Bidu-Dubbi volcanic system is seated on the southern edge of the Arrata block (earlier called “Danakil Alps”), a piece of Precambrian basement, with its Mesozoic sedimentary cover, locally covered by trap basalts dated circa 30My. These Pre-Tertiary units, deeply affected by normal faulting - of NNW-SSE (Red Sea) direction – are remnants from the Arabo-Nubian dome seen as an effect of the early Afar mantle plume.

2.1.2 Miocene peralkaline granite

As also seen on figure 1 & 3, these pre-rift series are intruded by peralkaline granites, as observed in Dioita (De Fino et al., 1978), a magmatic unit similar as the ones found along the Nubian plateau margin (Limmo) and in central Afar (Affara Dara), all dated between 22 and 24 My. A date considered by Barberi et al. (1972) as marking the initiation of the Afar rift (see also Varet, 2018).

2.1.3 Plio-pleistocene units

Underlying the Bidu-Dubbi volcanic centres, the basaltic piles of the Dalha formation (8-4 My) outcropping north cover in discordance these earlier units north (De Fino et al., 1978). To the south, products of these volcanoes cover the mio-pliocene polychromatic detrital units developed at the foot of the Arrata block, whereas the Afar stratoid series (3 to 1 My) outcrops on the south side (Figure 4).

Figure 4: Geological map of the Bidu-Dubbi area, extracted from the CNR-CNRS 1/500.00 map of northern Afar (1973). The pre-Miocene formations are mapped in pale brown, the polychromatic detrital unit is pictured in brown, the Afar stratoid series in green, recent quaternary basalts in blue and rhyolitic pyroclastic products in orange. Recent quaternary sediments are pictured in yellow, and white for the flat-lying floor of the Afar depression. Observe the NE-SW trend of these major units, and the E-W Ado Ale alignment of basaltic scoria cones West of Assab, along the 13°N meridian.

2.2 A major geological discontinuity

The Dubbi-Bidu volcanic units are fairly recent. They developed in the last million year, through a recurrent activity continuing until present, with several historical eruptions recorded

and a good number of age determinations tracing successive events in the last 400 ky. Whereas the whole Afar floor is fully controlled, in this northern half (between 12°N and 15°N) by a tectonic trend of NNW-SSE direction, which is the one of the Red Sea Rift, the Bidu-Dubbi volcano-tectonic system is dominated by transverse structures cutting through this regional trend. The volcanic centers, both basaltic scoria cones and feeding dikes and large silicic stratovolcanoes appear to have developed along a NE-SW tectonic direction.

In this area bordering the Afar triangle along the Red Sea coast, large amount of recent volcanic units, made of both basaltic and silicic products, developed along transverse directions: the Bidu-Dubbi alignment (NE-SW) and the Assab alignment trending E-W (Figure 4). Similar units are in fact found on both sides of the Afar rift, as seen on Figure 3.

2.2.1 The transverse volcanic units

As shown by Barberi et al. (1974), compared with the axial ranges – which are the present axis of oceanic spreading along the Afar floor - made of transitional basalts of tholeiitic affinity, these equally recent units of the Afar margins are characterized by a contrasting volcanology and petrology, with:

- Silicic pyroclastic products, emitted from stratovolcanoes showing signs of crustal contamination (Barberi et al., 1972);
- Alkaline basalts with frequent peridotite and other ultra-basic nodules as found in Ado Ale (Assab) range (De Fino et al., 1973).

2.2.2. Extension in the Red Sea: the Hannish Islands

The Bidu-Dubbi volcanic system, already impressive per se, appears in fact to be part of a much larger active volcano-tectonic megastructure that extends to the East in the Red Sea. The Hannish islands developed along the same NE-SW faulting and diking system transverse with respect to the Red Sea, and correspond with the dying of the Red Sea trough, which is well marked and active north but absent south in the Bab-El-Mandeb straight.

2.2.3 Extension across the Afar floor and the Nubian plateau

Towards West an important geological discontinuity is observed across the Afar floor, with the termination of the Tat'Ali and Alayta axial ranges, replaced south by the active Manda Inakir segment, which developed a spectacular event in the years 2005-2010, with an opening reaching locally 7m wide over a length of 70 Km. In fact the discontinuity also affect the Nubian escarpment, along the Dabbayra transverse volcanic shield and associated NE-SW basaltic alignment.

2.2.4 The southern extremity of Arrata rotating block and the Arabian plate accretion

Worth to note is the fact that, south from these units, the geology of the Afar margin is radically different, with no pre-Mesozoic formation observed at the surface, but only volcanic units of mio-pliocene age (Marinelli & Varet, 1972). These units therefore developed along a major discontinuity in the plate-tectonics arrangement, with (as seen in Figure5):

- the Arrata block affected by an anticlockwise rotation to the north, and
- an accretion of the Arabian plate to the south (Barberi & Varet, 1977; Varet, 2019,).

As a result, the Bidu-Dubbi alignment and its extension in the Red Sea and in Central Afar can be considered as a major fracture zone, leaking due to extensional components resulting from the rotation of the Arrata block. The magmatic evolution observed along this segment, from

large silicic centers in Bidu to dominantly basaltic units in Dubbi directly relates to the wider opening resulting from the rotation of Arrata block (Figure 5)

Fig.5: Microplate interpretation of the Afar active volcano-tectonic and hydrothermal manifestations showing the Bidu (Bi) – Dubbi (Di) transverse (NE-SW) alignment.

The motion of the Arabia plate with respect to Nubia (2 cm/y) is pictured with the red arrow.

It appears to be part of a major transverse fault zone (TFZ) linking Hanish Islands (HI, south of which the Red Sea trough dies), to Dabbayra (Da) transverse volcanic unit (also marking an offset of the Nubian basement) through Dubbi (Di), Bidu (Bi) and Dabbahu (Du).

The axial ranges, present axis of spreading along the Afar floor are figured in grey.

The anticlockwise rotation of the Arrata block relates with the progressive dying of the Red Sea spreading axis and the increase of spreading rates within Afar southwards. It also induces an increasing “leaking” from SW to NE along the Budu-Dubbi TFZ, that directly reflects in the volcanology and petrology, with increasing basaltic activity towards the Red Sea.

From Barberi & Varet, 1977, modified.

2.3. The Bidu-Dubbi volcanic units

Besides a large number of smaller scoria and spatter cones, five major volcanic centres are identified along this single NE-SW trend. By order of importance these are (Figure 4):

2.3.1. Nabro volcano

Nabro, located in Eritrea, reaching an altitude of 2200 meters, is a stratovolcano characterized by a succession of ignimbrite eruptions which formed a 7Km wide summit caldera, open towards SW (Fig.6). It was affected by post-caldera eruptions, marked by domes, cones and flows and provided an important eruption in 2011 which induced the displacement of 12.000 people and a few deaths. It was therefore studied by several teams, among which Goitom et al., (2015) and Hamlyn et al., (2018).

2.3.2. Malhalle volcano

Mallahle volcano, located in Ethiopia, is seated SW of Nabro. It is a rather similar stratovolcano with a summit caldera more than 5 Km wide (Fig.6). The succession of the ignimbrite eruptions did interfere between both volcanoes, with major episodes dated 23.1 ka ; 62.0 ka ; 130 ka ; 157 ka with the earliest phases of pre-caldera activity dating back to circa 300 and 400 ka.

Both volcanoes are affected by fumarolic activity, with steam vents captured by the local population for water condensation, as there are no permanent sources of liquid water in the area, however populated by pastoralist Afar communities.

Figure 6: Digital Elevation Model (DEM) showing the relief of the active volcanic units of Dubbi and Nabro in Eritrea and Mallahle and Sork'Ale in Ethiopia.

Observe the well-defined NE-SW alignment of the main 3 units, but also NW-SE alignments of domes and scoria cones. Sork'Ale also appear as located along such faults of Red Sea direction. From Goitom et al., (2015)

2.3.3 Dubbi basaltic fissure

Dubbi, located in Eritrea, consists of a dominantly basaltic lava field, emitted from fissures and spatter cones trending NE-SW, and a few silicic centers, one of them (well visible on the DEM map Fig.6) known for its historical activity: a Plinian eruption was observed in 1961 causing the death of at least 175 people. It was studied in details by De Fino et al. (1977)

2.3.4 Sork'Ale volcano

A smaller silicic stratovolcano, 5 Km wide, with a crater 500m large at the top, is located on the SE flank of Mallahle volcano, also in Ethiopia. Called Sork'Ale, it appears as a rather recent unit, with still a significant fumarolic activity in the crater. Whereas the 4 first units are aligned along the same NE-SW trend, Sork'Ale appears as related to Mallahle through NNW-SSE (Red Sea) extensional faulting.

A third stratovolcano, with a caldera 7 to 5 Km wide, elongated along the same tectonic trend, is seated on the SW flank of Mallahle, in Ethiopia (Fig.4). It is a slightly older unit, with post-caldera eruptions partly hiding its SE flank.

3. A major geothermal target

As a whole, the geodynamic context, the geological history, the present-day thermal and volcanic activity and the detailed understanding of the geology allows to consider the area as a major geothermal target, although properly unstudied as such yet. Within the whole range, we propose to left aside, to start with, the extreme units of Dubbi (dominantly fissural) Sork'Ale (a small target) and of the southernmost caldera (older), and concentrate the efforts on Nabro and Mallahle, the two most spectacular and equally recent stratovolcanoes both with calderas, and sitting along the Ethio-Eritrean boundary on each side of it.

3.1. Preliminary conceptual model

Besides the volcanology itself, which show a long-lasting diversified magmatic history (with important silicic products) over two areas of circa 50Km² each, the seismicity recorded after the Nabro volcanic event, as well as InSAR data modelling, show the presence of magma bodies at shallow depth within each volcano, as well as active fractures that should mark the presence of brittle reservoir conditions (Figure 7).

Figure 7: The upper map shows the hypocenter locations for the 658 earthquakes detected during the period 31 Aug. to 7 Oct. 2011, drawn as black dots (map view) and grey dots with error bars (N-S depth profile). The position of relocated hypocenters is shown as colored dots, dependent on their local magnitude. Seismic stations used to locate the events are indicated by black triangles. Yellow outlines the vent region.

Below: topographic profile and hypocenters along transect A-A'. The depths are given referenced to 700 m asl. The histogram shows numbers of hypocenters at depth per 1 km bin.

From Hamlyn et al., (2015)

It is of interest to note that the seismic campaign, based on the Nabro volcano itself did equally register a significant activity within Mallahle volcano also despite the lack of seismic stations there. Both appear to be fed by magma chambers at similar depth, with a brittle zone in the 4 to 7 Km depth interval (below 700m m.). This can be interpreted as a shallow heat source

overlaid by a brittle hydrothermal reservoir, regularly fractured by seismic activity along NE-SW and NW-SE fault lines crossing through the area.

The InSAR analysis of ascending and descending images, acquired after the eruption by the TSX satellite between 1 July 2011 and 10 October 2012, and developed by Hamling et al. (2015) shows a concentric subsidence signal centered on Nabro's caldera with a maximum rate of 20 cm/year, with a source at a depth of 6.9 ± 1.1 km. Their study also identifies, in conjunction with focal mechanisms, a major fault plane striking NE-SW with dips 45° to the SE, crosscutting the caldera floor and linked to a deeper magma source.

As seen on Figure 8, both units show a similar magmatic evolution, with a continuous crystal fractionation trend from transitional basalts to peralkaline trachyte and rhyolites,

Figure 8: Magmatic evolution of Nabro volcano. From Goitom et al., (2015)

As a whole, although rather similar in shape, magmatic evolution and structure at depth, Nabro and Mallahle volcanoes apparently display distinct magma chambers and geothermal systems. Given their proximity and similarity, they should however benefit from a joint approach in terms of surface studies and exploration drilling.

3.2. Benefit from a joint prefeasibility study

The benefit from a joint feasibility study engaged in the same time on both sides of the Ethio-Eritrea boundary, by scientific and technical teams from both countries, supported by a few international experts acquainted with the area would be multiple:

- For each of the two countries, as this sign of good-will and promotion of peace through shared challenge would be of high significance and ethical value.
- For the local communities in the area, which are at present affected by climate change and resulting recurrent draughts, as geothermal would bring two essential components answering the sustainable development goals: access to water and clean energy. Hence offering a solution of resilience, avoiding migrations, the only alternative at present.
- For the technical and scientific teams of both countries, with the national geological surveys at the front and the support of the best universities, from Addis Ababa, Asmara, Semera and Mekele. They are already engaged in surveys and research in the area, but separately, and would benefit from joint researches with the support of international research teams considering Afar as a major target.

- For the international, regional and bilateral donor agencies, who will all consider this project as one of the best possible option to be engaged in the region, with a visible result to be acquired in a few years delay due to a good coordination among donors and with concerned partners.

The surface study will require the classical approach, with:

- Geology, in particular volcano-structural and petro-mineralogical field and laboratory works, allowing to precise the nature of the reservoir, heat source and cover.
- The geoscientific studies would benefit from a digital elevation mapping using detailed satellite data and complementary drone surveys (LIDAR and Infra-Red)?
- Geochemistry of the fluids, after an hydrogeological study and an accurate mapping of all thermal manifestations and proper field sampling procedures, followed by geothermometric and hydrogeological modeling.
- Geophysical surveys, including: gravimetry, Magneto-telluric and micro-seismicity surveys allowing for 3D modelling through joint inversion of the data.

It should allow to locate sites for exploration drillings, to be located on both sides of the boundary, allowing to confirm the geothermal resource through production tests and to convince investors for the next development steps. Investors, public or private, should be interested by the perspective of contributing to a socio-economic development concerning an area where the population is in real need given the worsening climate conditions, after a long-lasting period of tension and even war.

3.3. Geothermal for Peace

Geothermal energy is not only a natural and renewable resource, which allows to replace fossil fuels for electricity generation, offering a continuous production serving the base load of the grid. A specificity that makes geothermal a necessary complement to other renewable sources, which are all intermittent and climate dependent. It is also a solution of resilience, particularly in arid areas where the need for water is even more important than the need for energy (Chandrasekharam, 2015). Geothermal is also a social issue, as the concerned population – in the present case, the Afar pastoralist communities – know the surface manifestations quite well. These are historically and still presently sources of water by condensation in case of draught (or even on a regular basis) and sites where the vegetation will benefit from wet grounds, source of fodder for their herds. It is even a gender issue, as women and girls are generally in charge of carrying water and energy (wood) eventually over long distances, in order to answer the needs of the settlement.

Besides answering the needs of the local population, these geothermal sites should also feed the grid that would serve the cities and ports along the Red Sea shore (including Assab) as well as the sites inland, particularly the mining and agro-pastoralist projects.

After a long period of unrest along this Ethio-Eritrean border, including recurrent wars, time has come to consider this border, not as a matter of confrontation, but a matter of joint challenge, for the development of a sustainable resource, hence a source of sustained peace and socio-economic welfare.

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